

MPOWERBIO

eM-POWERing SME Clusters to help SMEs to overcome the valley of death

D1.3 Workshop co-created design of capacity building and business support programmes

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Bio-based Industries Consortium

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4	Corporacion Tecnologica de Andalucia https://www.corporaciontecnologica.com/es/	CTA	ES	Non-profit Research Centre/Cluster
5	Italbiotec https://www.italbiotec.it/	IBT	IT	Non-profit Research Centre/Cluster
6	FoodScale Hub https://foodscaleshub.com/	FSH	RS	Non-profit Association /Cluster
7	EIT Food https://www.eitfood.eu/	EIT	BE	Non-profit Association
8	Irish Bioeconomy Foundation https://bioeconomyfoundation.com/	IBF	IE	Non-profit SME/Cluster
9	Q-Plan International https://qplan-intl.gr/	QPL	GR	SME
10	Sustainable Innovations Europe https://www.sustainableinnovations.eu/	SIE	ES	SME

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1. Executive summary

The MPowerBIO project will obtain feedback from clusters, SMEs and investors on the concrete challenges they have regarding investments and build an online platform containing digital tools for evaluating investment readiness, as well as online training modules to build the capacity of clusters to train their SME members.

This document describes the development of task 1.3: Co-design MPowerBIO's capacity building and business support programmes (M3-M6). To this end, an online co-creation workshop event took place on the 29th of October 2020. It was led by Sustainable Innovation (SIE) as part of the Work Package (WP) 1, which main objective is setting up the MPowerBIO capacity building for clusters and business support programmes.

This project has received funding from the Bio Based Industries Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 887501.

1.1 Context of WP1

The objectives of this WP are:

- * Map available investment sources and shed light on their requirements to get insight into how SMEs can better select, prepare for and capture financial opportunities suitable for their projects.
- * Analyse the skill gaps and training needs of clusters to develop practical steps to train the trainers, empowering them to support SMEs in preparing for and securing investments.
- * Organise and run the MPowerBIO Co-Creation Workshop to engage key stakeholders in co-defining the capacity building and business support programmes of the project.
- * Develop the material required to operationalise and deliver the capacity building programme of MPowerBIO to clusters, as well as its business support programme to their SMEs.
- * Set up and operate an Advisory Board comprised by key experts and professionals to be strategically integrated in the project's activities and provide meaningful advice.

1.2 Objective of Task 1.3

The aim of Task 1.3 is to set the stage for the development of the capacity building and business support programmes.

1.3 Specific actions for the co-creation workshop

The consortium was expected to invite representatives from financial instruments such as EIB/EIF, industry experts suggested by BIC, private and corporate investors. Selected representatives of the stakeholders as well as members of the Advisory Board were also expected to be invited (25-30 participants) to participate.

2. About the Project

Many SMEs experience that even though they have a good idea or a good product, they cannot get an investor. They need to be able to pitch their idea perfectly, have a strong business plan, a clear strategy, a well-defined customer base, etc. to attract investors.

European clusters need to be better suited to help small and medium sized enterprises (SMEs) overcome the valley of death i.e. the difficult task of finding sufficient investment to get from idea to business. This is the main focus of the MPowerBIO project.

In the MPowerBIO project 10 training the trainers' events will be arranged for a total of 90 clusters across the bioeconomy, covering most of Europe. The events are set up to help clusters understand how SMEs can obtain capital and grow.

Online training modules and regional trainers' events will be organised to build the capacity of clusters to train their SME members and give them the best possibilities for preparing and presenting high quality projects to investors.

The best SME projects from these events will be selected by investors, and invited to one of two European finals, At the final, the selected companies will present their ideas to a panel of investors and experts from large organisations and venture funds in Europe, with the aim of attracting capital to grow and develop their business.

A total of 72 high-quality, screened and investment-ready SMEs are expected to pitch at the two final events. The project will screen and support 250 SMEs towards this goal.

3. Introduction

The MPowerBIO Co-creation Workshop, led by SIE, was held in the very beginning of the project (M6). The main purpose of this event was to co-design MPowerBIO's capacity building and business support programmes.

This co-creation workshop addressed key stakeholders from SMEs, clusters, financial instruments' representatives, investors, and industry experts with the intention to introduce them the proposed concepts and findings, with a view to soliciting meaningful feedback and novel ideas.

This deliverable will analyse and discuss the objectives of the event and its organisational aspects, the feedback from the attendees and, to avoid any errors being repeated, lessons learned from the entire process pre- and post- the event.

- According to the Description of the Action, the workshop was planned to be an in-person workshop, but the current COVID-19 situation and the existing restrictions imposed a barrier to celebrate physical events, so it was needed to transform it into an online event.
- The deliverable was expected to be submitted on M6 (end of October 2020) but it was delayed until M7 (end of November 2020) due to a change in its organisation method, namely from a face-to-face event to an online seminar. Moreover, the initial idea to provide input to the development of form and content for the capacity building and business support programmes, was adapted to the validation of a pre-prepared draft. In order to carry out such a validation process, it was necessary to have a draft ready that the participants can relate to and qualify. At the same time, this draft was highly dependent on the results from T1.1 "Mapping existing investment sources and revealing their requirements" and T1.2 "Analysing available and missing skills to identify training needs", both delayed scheduled to be completed by September 2020 but were delayed for one month due to COVID 19 crisis. Overall, the one-month delay in preparing this deliverable was communicated to the Project Officer and was accepted.

4. Organisational aspects

Even if this was planned to be a physical event, it was needed to change the organisation and to create an online workshop that was held on October 29th, 2020 from 10:00 to 12:30 (CET). SIE coordinated the online session which was joined by all the project partners, with some of them having a more active participation by presenting general aspects of the MPowerBIO project, the proposed concepts for the capacity building & business support programmes, the moderation of the discussions and the presentation of final conclusions of the co-creation activities carried out.

It was required to organise two breakout sessions as the workshop was intended to collect ideas for both the capacity building and the business support programmes. In that sense, after the brief presentations, the participants were split into 2 parallel 'rooms' and two different sessions were created: (i) A session dedicated to the capacity building programme for clusters with a view to co-creating the curriculum concept, key training topics and delivery methods to be used for its operations; and (ii) a session focused on co-creating the services to be delivered by clusters in the consortium and associated clusters through the business support programme to SMEs. Both sessions dedicated time to engage participants in co-defining specific KPIs for the monitoring and evaluation system of their respective programmes.

4.1 Tools used

SIE decided to use [GoToTraining](#), as it had previous good experience using this tool in other similar activities. In addition, this tool records the session, provides extra security against hacking, allows to create breakout sessions and to gather insights and feedback from the attendees.

As it was mentioned before, the participants were requested to provide novel ideas and meaningful feedback so it was needed to use another online tool for capturing all the ideas and to help them grow into concepts and conclusions. [Miro](#) was the selected tool as it offers an easy to use collaboration whiteboard that allows to collect input from brainstorming in real time.

4.2 Agenda and speakers

SIE was in charge of moderating the main session of the event, including: its opening, providing general instructions, launching icebreaker questions, presenting the speakers, sharing the presentation slides through GoToTraining's "Share screen" function, and managing the breakout sessions.

Some of the partners presented different topics in the workshop including a brief introduction of the project that was made by Britt Sandvad, coordinator of MPowerBio and Senior innovation Manager at Food & Bio Cluster (FBCD), while Maja Žikić, Growth Lead at FoodScaleHub (FSH) was in charge of presenting the capacity building & business support programmes for clusters. In the breakout sessions, FSH (Maja Žikić and Mladen Radisic) participated as moderator of the 2 breakout sessions and SIE provided technical support. Technical Corporation of Andalusia (CTA) and CLIB actively participated as technical leaders during the breakout sessions and they were also responsible for summarising the conclusions of the workshop. Annex I show the agenda with the topics and partners involved.

4.3 Tools for event dissemination

Eventbrite was the chosen platform by SIE to create an [event page](#) and manage the registrations, as it helped to reach a bigger audience and make it easy for them to have detailed information about the workshop, including the agenda.

Figure 1. Event page in Eventbrite

Figure 2. Shared agenda

A [social media announcement](#) was also made through MPowerBIO's LinkedIn managed by FBCD, and this was further shared by the consortium partners and personal social media accounts. This announcement included the direct link to the Eventbrite page, so it was easier for the interested participants to register.

Figure 3. Post on the project LinkedIn profile

4.4 Methodology and content of the main session

Before the workshop, SIE organised a rehearsal to guarantee that the platform run smoothly with the main partners involved. SIE also shared a document with the consortium partners which included the Frequent Ask Questions (FAQ) that could arise regarding the development of the workshop, and the use of GoToTraining and Miro.

Figure 4. FAQ 1-4

FAQ : MPOWERBIO co creation workshop

5. How interventions are organised during the workshop?

This is the internal agenda, for the consortium to be aware:

- 10:00-10:05. Event opening and welcome. Instructions on how to use the tools. Launch Icebreaker questions. Mariana Fernández (SIE).
- 10:05-10:10 Brief presentation on MpowerBIO scope, objectives and KPIs. Britt Sandvad (FBC).
- 10:10-10:30 Capacity building & business support programmes for SME clusters. Maja Zikic (FSH)
- 10:30-10:40 Launch questions to audience, invitation to join the Breakout sessions & brief instructions. Mariana Fernández (SIE).
- 10:40:11:55 Breakout session 1: Capacity building programmes for SME clusters. Miro platform. Support: Ana Martínez (SIE). Moderator: Maja Zikic (FSH). Technical leader and minutes: Tatjana Schwabe (CLIB)
- 10:40:11:55 Breakout session 2: Business support programmes. Miro platform. Support: Jeisel Goyanes (SIE). Moderator: Mladen Radisic (FSH). Technical leader and minutes: María García (CTA)
- 11:55-12:05 Conclusions from technical leaders. Tatjana Schwabe (CLIB) and María García (CTA)
- 12:05-12:10 Wrap up and closing. Mariana Fernández (SIE).

Figure 5. FAQ 5

FAQ : MPOWERBIO co creation workshop

6. Will the questions just pop-up?

The icebreaker questions will be launched through the poll system of the tool. Results will be later shown on the screen, after voting. While we organise the breakout rooms a couple of questions will be launched out loud, just to entertain the audience while they wait to be divided in groups.

7. How is the audience going to answer those questions?

We will remind them to write down on the chat their questions. All participants except from the speakers will be muted to avoid echos.

8. Who is going to moderate the questions?

SIE will answer the questions related to the operation of the tool. Technical leaders and moderators are encouraged to answer the questions on the chat. If a question is directly addressed to Britt or Maja, Mariana will ask both of them at the end of their presentations to please answer out loud. If a question can't be answered because it's too complex or long, we can inform the attendees that we'll respond to it in a follow up email after the session.

Figure 6. FAQ 6-8

FAQ : MPOWERBIO co creation workshop

9. If no one is participating actively, what shall we do?

Consortium partners are encouraged to please prepare a set of questions & answers to animate the conversation and launch them on the chat, if necessary. During the breakout sessions they could also contribute through postsits.

10. How are the breakout sessions organised?

The tool divides automatically the participants. We will make sure that the technical leaders, moderators and support are in the correct room.

11. Are all the participants participating in both sessions?

Yes, they are. The first round session will consist of 45 minutes. The second one will only last for 30 minutes as participants will start from the conclusions the other group obtained.

12. How do we switch rooms when the session is over?

Mariana (SIE) will be in charge of changing only the technical leaders, moderators and support to the other room. The rest of the participants will remain in the same room.

Figure 7. FAQ 9-12

FAQ : MPOWERBIO co creation workshop

13. What is the difference between the roles of support, moderator and technical leader?

The role of support will be led by SIE. They will only be in charge of the technical problems regarding the tool. They will be also reading the chat in case something comes up. Most importantly, they will be the **ONLY** ones sharing the screen.

Moderators (Maja and Mladen) will have to explain briefly at the beginning of each session how to operate with the platform (Miro) and give a couple of instructions on how the audience should respond and when. They will guide the discussions based on the questions.

Tehcnical leaders (Mária and Tatjana) will help with the answers, they will group them on the platform (Miro) if similar responses may arise. They will support on encouraging the audience. And, most importantly, they will be taking notes as they should be providing a couple of outputs in the conclusion part of the workshop, once the breakout session is over.

14. How do I connect to the Miro platform?

A link will be sent to participants on the breakout session chat, for everyone to connect and participate from their computers.

Logo: Bio-based Industries Consortium, European Union, MPOWERBIO

www.mpowerbio.eu

Figure 8. FAQ 13-14

FAQ : MPOWERBIO co creation workshop

15. I'm not much familiar on how Miro works, how do I manage?

Moderators will provide instructions at the beginning of the session but moderators, technical leaders and support are encouraged to familiarise with the tool before the event. Mariana will send the board in advance to make this possible.

16. Sharing the screen during the breakout session seems not to work. What do I do?

We've experienced some technical problems in this regard during the rehearsals. It is not critical, as the important thing here is for every participant to have their own Miro board opened in their own laptops or PC. If that happens, the support will remind participants to use Miro.

17. My micro does not seem to work, what do I do?

Check first if it is muted. If it is not, check the output on the settings menu and try selecting a different source.

18. I have not receive the link to connect, how do I do it?

Check first your spam folder in case the invitation went there. If not, you can connect on: www.jointraining.com and introduce the following code: 709-012-028

Logo: Bio-based Industries Consortium, European Union, MPOWERBIO

www.mpowerbio.eu

Figure 9. FAQ 15-18

The format of the co-creation workshop was based on different live presentations and interactive sessions with the audience (including two breakout sessions) to gather general insights on GoToTraining and see ideas posted on the Miro boards.

SIE was the moderator, in charge of doing the introduction to the workshop, transitioning between presentations, moderating the questions and interactions with the participants, dividing the attendees into two main groups for each of the breakout sessions and providing technical support on Miro boards. During the entire webinar, SIE was able to see who was connected, and all the comments or questions in the chat.

Figure 10. Agenda included in the presentation

Figure 11. Instructions provided at the beginning of the webinar

Figure 12. Food & Bio Cluster Denmark presentation

Figure 13. FoodScale Hub presentation

After the two presentations, the participants were encouraged to participate in the co-creation sessions. They all had the opportunity to co-create in the two running sessions, one for the capacity building programme and the other for the business support programme.

Figure 14. Instructions provided for the co-creation sessions during the workshop

As part of the agenda, the participants returned to the main session after the co-creation sessions ended. The final conclusions were explained by CLIB and CTA, and SIE was in charge of closing the workshop.

Figure 15. Conclusions from the co-creation sessions

Figure 16. Closure of the workshop

4.5 Methodology and content of the co-creation sessions

As it was explained before, SIE oversaw the creation of the two breakout sessions in GoToTraining. From their side, FSH developed all the content that was integrated in Miro panels (designed by SIE) to collect ideas from the attendees, which were divided into four building blocks:

1. Problems & Solutions Breakdown
2. Categorisation and Scoring
3. Crazy-8
4. Feedback & Closing

FSH started each session by explaining the objectives and expected results of the breakout session, the rules, and letting participants explore Miro briefly. The instruction and the time slots for the four blocks were included as notes in the Miro platform, so it was easy for the participants to have a look at them when needed.

There was a difference between the questions asked in the first block for the Capacity Building Programme and the Business Support Programme, as they were expected to provide new ideas based on the specific session they were part of. Apart from this difference, all the four blocks required the same kind of participation from the attendees. The specific questions of block 1 and the functioning and expected outcomes of the following 3 blocks can be found in Annex II.

Figure 17. Design of the Miro board

Figure 20. Business support programmes - Block 3

Figure 21. Capacity building programmes - Block 1

Figure 22. Capacity building programmes - Block 2

4.6 Materials provided

A follow up email was sent to all the attendees, where they could find an invitation to visit the project website: <https://mpowerbio.eu/>, and the MPowerBIO YouTube channel where the recordings were uploaded. They were also invited to follow the project on LinkedIn and to evaluate the workshop in case they were not able to do so during the session.

Figure 23. Follow-up email

4.7 Participants

A total of 83 participants registered, of which 60 joined the main session of the workshop. For the breakout sessions the number decreased to 45, of which 32 actively participated in the co-creation session and the ideas brainstorming in Miro.

Apart from the participation of consortium members, the attendees came from a wide range of organisations and sectors, all of which were sectors targeted by the consortium. These included several SMEs: Imegen, Bioc-Chemsolutions, Alchemia-nova, or Dnd biotech. Some cluster representatives were also part of the workshop: Biocluster, Avebiom, and Bioeconomy foundation. The Bio-based Industry Consortium and other types of organisations from the sector also attended session as: Cener or Novamont. Hefr as policymaker and Business Angels Connect as investor also joined the workshop.

Figure 24. Icebreaker question 1

In relation to the different expectations that the attendees had, it was found that the majority of them wanted to learn more about the capacity building and business support programme, and some of them wanted to contribute to the programmes based on their experience and to know more about the MPowerBIO project.

Figure 25. Icebreaker question 2

4.8 Discussion and engagement

During the workshop, participants had the opportunity to contribute to the event through the chat section with their questions or comments. At the beginning, an attendee wanted to be sure that we will send all the presentations afterwards.

The second presentation of the workshop about capacity building & business support programmes for SME clusters, sparked the interest to deepen the information related to funding opportunities and how they are arranged on a local and national level. Then, the speakers talked about national and regional funding mechanisms.

The participants also showed interest in the functioning of the breakout sessions, including the links to join them and how they will have the opportunity to participate in both.

4.9 Feedback

As it was an online event, the consortium decided to receive feedback in two ways. As GoToTraining allows to collect insights from the participants, the first one consisted in encouraging them at the end of the session to answer different questions, being one of them “How would you evaluate this workshop?“. Five options were given to rate the workshop: 1 person voted for “Poor” and other one voted for “Very bad”, “Average” was selected by 2 people, “Good” and “Very good” were voted by 5 people each; with a total of 14 people providing feedback at the end of the session.

The second way was to share a link in the follow-up email to facilitate that the people who could not participate until the end of the session could also provide feedback about the workshops. This feedback was intended to be more specific, so 4 different questions were included. We received the evaluation of 9 people, with 7 out of 9 recommending the workshop to a colleague.

How would you rate this webinar overall?	How would you rate the contents?	How would you rate the length?	Would you recommend it to a friend/colleague?
Very good	Very good	I would prefer it to be a bit shorter	Yes
Good	Very good	I would prefer it to be a bit shorter	Yes
Good	Good	I would prefer it to be a bit shorter	Yes
Bad	Bad	Good	No
Average	Average	I would prefer it to be a bit shorter	Yes
Very good	Very good	Good	Yes
Average	Average	I would prefer it to be a bit shorter	No
Good	Good	Good	Yes
Good	Very good	Good	Yes

Figure 6. Evaluation of the workshop

4.10 Dissemination afterwards

The entire session was recorded and shared as a follow up email to all those who registered. In addition, it was uploaded to [YouTube](#):

4.11 Lessons learnt from the co-creation workshop

Lessons learned from the Co-creation workshop, concerning the Capacity building programme:

- As for the *program delivery*, the participants generally agreed that the program should be held online, but also include some in-person meetings. As a reason for this, they stated that the personal exchange is considered very important for rapport building and exchange of best practice ideas.
- When asked about *who the program should target*, the participants suggested that it should be focused on those in clusters who support SMEs and their business-oriented aspects, but should also include cluster managers when it comes to strategic orientations or decisions.
- Regarding the *type of content* that the participants would like to see in the programme, it was agreed upon the fact that soft skills would be very important for SMEs; next it was suggested to have the sharing of success stories in order to learn from them and maybe also even inspire

other SMEs; and on a more technical level – how to assess business model viability and how to communicate it to investors.

- The participants were also asked about the *funding landscape* that they are working in, and where they identify problems and would like to see some answers. All levels seem to be interesting to the participants, from spin-outs to more mature SMEs, and the most pressing problems appear to be: how to assess the risk profile. and how to catch exactly the right time to contact investors for funding while also deciding which investors should be contacted.
- In the end, the participants were asked to share their *expectations from the programme* in the form of benefits they are hoping to obtain. The answers ranged from: improved cluster services for their SMEs and start-ups, connecting to investors beyond their own region where they are already active and knowledgeable, to gaining a better overview of trends and investors' interests.

Lessons learned from the Co-creation workshop, concerning the Business support programme:

- Regarding the *program features and target groups*, the participants agreed upon a blended format as the best option for this kind of programme. The reason is that even though we are getting used to using the online tools, the offline activities remain of interest for the participants.
- As for the *type of content*, the participants suggested short, sharp content modules. In other words, they would like for the program to be flexible, with short modules but with high-level content.
- When asked who the *most qualified person* would be to attend the programme, the answer was that this depends on the particular SME size and structure. Sometimes SMEs have innovation managers and therefore entrepreneurs responsible, but that is not always the case. For those SMEs with fewer people, the CTO or the CFO would be the most suitable person for following the programme.
- Another question asked was regarding *the needs identified by SMEs* at the beginning of the programme. Some of the issues highlighted by the participants are issues regarding the viability of their business model, where to get funding, how to get niches or opening markets, reaching users and presenting them the new value proposition.
- In the end, the participants were asked to share their *expectations of the programme* in terms of different aspects that the programme could cover. The primary expectation is that the general impression of their challenges would be improved and that they would be able to overcome them, especially those linked to their funding and unlocking finance, networking, obtaining connections, coaching sessions, and their funding or investment runs.

The organisation of the final conference was a success, and this was possible because of all the efforts done by the consortium partners collectively bringing all their skills together. Anyway, we still have some aspects to improve as to coordinate ourselves better in the consortium, try to avoid last minute changes in the organisation (unless necessary) and have contents ready at least one week in advance for the rehearsal.

During the organisation of the workshop and on the actual live session, a few challenges arose, which the organisers had to overcome. We include here a list of different problems that we have identified and how they can be solved for future events:

- As of the current COVID-19 pandemic, this workshop was intended to be an in-person event, but it was not possible. The online alternative was the best option as it also brought several advantages as cost-saving or making it easier to engage a bigger amount of people since there was no need for travelling or consuming a lot of time in reaching the venue. However, this kind of event also includes some disadvantages as there is no face-to-face time to network or to increase the need of some basic knowledge about online tools. In this sense, the organisers tried to create a comfortable atmosphere since the beginning of the workshop, by hosting an icebreaking session and by encouraging to actively participate in the breakout sessions. It can be helpful to start with a round table for everyone to introduce themselves.
- GoToTraining have different features which placed it as the best option for hosting this online event as providing a personal link to each attendee for joining the session, preventing unidentified people from joining, and allowing to track how much time each attendee spends connected. Moreover, the possibility to create different breakout sessions, easily sharing the screen and muting all the attendees' microphones and cameras seemed to be exactly what was needed for a successful workshop. Nonetheless, the workshop experienced recurring sound problems and it was difficult for the organisers to manage the breakout sessions. In this way, we recommend:
 - To avoid breakouts or to have somebody to manage it on the background before the main session is over
 - Evaluate other available platforms which can reduce the recurring sound problems as Zoom
- Miro was the online tool used for the co-creation sessions as we considered it to be very easy to use, to create post its, to group ideas and gathered them in a way that is visual attractive. We consider that it is important to provide a tutorial on how to use Miro (or similar platforms) before the sessions kicks off as it would have been simpler for the participants.
- In addition, it seemed that the co-creation sessions were too complicated for the participants as they seemed a bit lost, so we encourage that for future events, interactive sessions should not be too complicated, especially when the time is limited. It is also relevant to think about new and better ways to encourage attendees to participate, we suggest to provide clear questions and pre-prepared answers, to leave the possibility to vote other answers and to be more clear about how they are invited to participate (micro, chat, directly posting their ideas)
- One of the lessons learnt from other similar events, and applied to this workshop, was to have only the organiser showing the slides of all the presentations, to save time and to avoid changing the roles in the platform. Beforehand, we were also aware of the slight delay on the slides passing, so we counted with that.
- For us, it was important that all the speakers, moderators and technical leaders could be familiarised with the GoToTraining and Miro platforms, so it was needed to conduct platform tests before the event to guarantee that everything runs smoothly.

Annexes

Annex I. Co-creation workshop agenda

10:00-10:05. Event opening and welcome. Instructions on how to use the tools. Launch icebreaker questions. Mariana Fernández (SIE).

10:05-10:10 Brief presentation on MpowerBIO scope, objectives and KPIs. Britt Sandvad (FBC).

10:10-10:30 Capacity building & business support programmes for SME clusters. Maja Zikic (FSH)

10:30-10:40 Launch questions to audience, invitation to join the Breakout sessions & brief instructions. Mariana Fernández (SIE).

10:40-11:55 Breakout session 1: Capacity building programmes for SME clusters. Miro platform. Support: Ana Martínez (SIE). Moderator: Maja Zikic (FSH). Technical leader and minutes: Tatjana Schwabe-Marković (CLIB)

10:40-11:55 Breakout session 2: Business support programmes. Miro platform. Support: Jeisel Goyanes (SIE). Moderator: Mladen Radisic (FSH). Technical leader and minutes: María García (CTA)

11:55-12:05 Conclusions from technical leaders. Tatjana Schwabe- Marković (CLIB) and María García (CTA)

12:05-12:10 Wrap up and closing. Mariana Fernández (SIE).

Annex II. Content and instructions for the Miro board

MPowerBIO Capacity Building Program

<p>Block #1 Problems & Solutions Breakdown (25 minutes/ 18 minutes 2nd session)</p> <p>In this block, each participant will list down as many relevant answers they can think of for the associated question in a short amount of time and put it on the Miro collaborative board. No duplicate answers. If so, rate others answers through emojis.</p> <p>Program features and target groups</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>What is the ideal capacity program location (on-site, off-site) and structure (content-medium-frequency)?</i> 2. <i>Who is the most qualified person to receive capacity building training (cluster manager, business innovation advisor or mentor, fund manager, etc.) and what is the best way to reach them?</i> 3. <i>Do the features of the capacity building program fit the needs of participants (prioritization and level of urgency)?</i> <p>Investment and funding landscape</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. <i>What is the typical venture stage of your members/ clients (pre-seed, seed or VC series)?</i> 5. <i>What kind of funding was raised (equity, debt, grants)?</i> 6. <i>How long does it take for your clients/ members to reach key funding milestones?</i> <p>Impact on change</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7. <i>What kind of metrics would be relevant for the capacity building program in terms of:</i> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. <i>Resources and capabilities</i> b. <i>Performance</i> c. <i>Socio-economic</i>
<p>Block #2 Categorization and Scoring (5 minutes)</p> <p>When the time for individual brainstorming ends, participants to give score 1, 2, 3 or 4 being 4 the best answer. Participants to move their post its to the second block.</p>
<p>Block #3 Crazy-8 (5 minutes)</p> <p>The Crazy-8 is the visual display of the ideas thrown by each participant. This visual representation is imperative to gain common ground of what the capacity building program should look like. We'll peak the best 6 answers for each question and two more relevant ones.</p>
<p>Block #4 Feedback & Closing (5 minutes)</p> <p>We will wrap up our sessions by quickly collecting feedback from participants and presenting a summary of our findings</p>

MPowerBIO Business Support Programme

<p>Block #1 Problems & Solutions Breakdown (25 minutes/ 18 minutes 2nd session)</p>
<p>In this block, each participant will list down as many relevant answers they can think of for the associated question in a short amount of time and put it on the Miro collaborative board. No duplicate answers. If so, rate others answers through emojis</p> <p>Program features and target groups</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>What is the ideal business support program location (on-site, off-site) and structure (content-medium-frequency)?</i> 2. <i>Who is the most qualified person to receive business support and investment readiness training (CEO, CTO or a manager for another important position) and what is the best way to reach them?</i> 3. <i>Do the features of the business support program fit the needs of participants (prioritization and level of urgency)?</i> <p>Business Support & Investment Readiness</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. <i>What would be the most important needs identified by SMEs at the time of application?</i> 5. <i>What aspects of the MPowerBIO business support program do startups/ SMEs identify as providing the greatest value during both the program and post-graduation?</i> <p>SMEs' performance</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. <i>What kind of metrics would be relevant for the business support program in terms of:</i> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. <i>Resources and capabilities</i> b. <i>Performance</i> c. <i>Socio-economic impacts</i>
<p>Block #2 Categorization and Scoring (5 minutes)</p>
<p>When the time for individual brainstorming ends, participants to give score 1, 2, 3 or 4 being 4 the best answer. Participants to move their post its to the second block.</p>
<p>Block #3 Crazy-8 (5 minutes)</p>
<p>The Crazy-8 is the visual display of the ideas thrown by each participant. This visual representation is imperative to gain common ground of what the capacity building program should look like. We'll peak the best 6 answers for each question and two more relevant ones.</p>
<p>Block #4 Feedback & Closing (5 minutes)</p>
<p>We will wrap up our sessions by quickly collecting feedback from participants and presenting a summary of our findings</p>